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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document outlines the design, implementation, and outcomes of a demonstrator developed to support interoperable and secure access to cancer genomic datasets across multiple European research infrastructures. The work was carried out collaboratively across several institutions (BSC, CSC, EMBL-EBI, and UMCG) and addresses key goals of federated data sharing and access within the context of the project's objectives.

The demonstrator is structured around three main parts.

The first part involves the ingestion and distribution of synthetic datasets (T1.2) via the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA). This includes the development of user interfaces and authentication mechanisms based on the European Life Sciences authentication and authorisation Infrastructure (LS AAI), as well as the integration of Globus as a secure, robust, and user-friendly data distribution system. Users are able to authenticate using a single identity across platforms, request access to datasets, and retrieve authorised data via secure Globus endpoints.

The second part involves linking the EOSC4Cancer data catalogue to the GDI domain specific data catalogue for genomics. This includes the semantic annotation of the EOSC4Cancer catalogue using DCAT-AP v3 and the subsequent harvesting of the DCAT record by the GDI data portal. In addition, we expanded EOSC4Cancer with a shopping cart to enable researchers to find and select data based on their very rich descriptions in EOSC4Cancer catalogue, and then hand-over to the GDI genomics data catalogue (inspired by BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator workflow). With this, members from the cancer community can seamlessly use GDI infrastructure to request and access genomics data.

The third part focuses on federated access through the Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI), with datasets hosted at two sites: CSC and UMCG. Here, users authenticate via LS AAI and access sensitive data within a secure, remote environment prepared by CSC. In addition, users are granted access to UMCG 'sandbox' inspired by Solve-RD. This setup simulates a high-compliance federated access model, where data remains within the infrastructure and analyses are performed remotely, satisfying stringent privacy and data governance requirements. Across both components, the demonstrator enables seamless interoperability between infrastructures and supports key FAIR principles. A unified identity layer, standardised access request workflows, and modular system design ensure scalability and adaptability to future use cases.

In addition to the core demonstrator functionality, the discussion section outlines future directions, including the incorporation of federated analysis capabilities through platforms like Galaxy, and integration with cancer analysis portals such as cBioPortal. These enhancements would enable users to run custom analyses across distributed datasets and streamline research workflows from data access to interpretation.

The demonstrator integrates all of the aspects of EOSC4Cancer WP1 including cancer data discovery from the data catalog (T1.1), leveraging the synthetic cancer datasets (T1.2), utilising GA4GH data standards (T1.3), into a federated data access workflow (T1.4). It successfully meets the goals of the deliverable by providing a practical and extensible framework for secure, federated data access across European genomic infrastructures, laying a strong foundation for continued innovation in the field of biomedical data sharing and analysis.

The BBMRI-ERIC pilot workflow presented here will lead to sustained fully operational services that contributed to future developments of the UNCAN-CONNECT and CANDLE projects, both starting in 2025 and adding to the EU Mission on Cancer.

A video recording of the demonstrator has been submitted to the [project drive](#).

1 Background

Cancer remains a major societal burden, particularly in Europe, which accounts for over 25% of global cancer cases despite comprising only 10% of the world's population. With ageing demographics, the number of long-term cancer survivors is projected to reach 13 million by 2035. Cancer's complexity—driven by genetics, environment, and lifestyle—demands advanced, data-enabled solutions for prevention, diagnosis, and treatment. However, survival rates have significantly improved in recent times due to innovations in diagnostics, therapeutics, and clinical research. Cutting-edge technologies have facilitated the discovery of cancer-specific biomarkers and driver genes. National and international cancer registries, clinical trials, and molecular studies have also generated unprecedented volumes of data. However, to fully harness this potential, these data streams must be interconnected and accessible across Europe.

The primary goal of EOSC4Cancer was to support the [EU Cancer Mission](#) by developing a federated digital infrastructure to enable secure access to federated cancer research data. The objectives of the project were to:

1. Enable storage, sharing, access, analysis and processing of research data and other digital research objects from basic and clinical cancer research.
2. Mobilise, interconnect and interoperate datasets relevant in cancer research.
3. Make cancer research data and analysis systems easily accessible to basic and clinical scientists in the most used cancer analysis portals.
4. Integrate digital tools, data analytics and Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning tools for the analysis of cancer data in the cancer analysis portals.
5. Contribute to the European Health Data Space (EHDS), the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and the Cancer Mission.

The first work package (WP1) of the EOSC4Cancer project—titled "Federated data spaces to enable accessing, using, reusing and sharing cancer-related data"—was dedicated to improving access to cancer-related data by enhancing the FAIRness of participating data resources through the adoption and extension of existing solutions. WP1 was structured around four key deliverables aimed at achieving these objectives: the development of both preliminary (D1.1) and final (D1.3) data resource maps for the contributing institutions; the generation of a high-quality synthetic dataset intended for use throughout and beyond the duration of the project (D1.4); and the demonstration of interoperable data access across distinct, federated infrastructures (D1.2).

The remainder of this report will describe the background and the work completed to fulfill these objectives as part of WP1, through deliverable D1.2.

2 Deliverable description

Genomic data is a critical component in cancer research and plays a central role in guiding cancer clinical decisions related to diagnosis and treatment. As national health systems and collaborative scientific initiatives expand, vast volumes of genetic, imaging, clinical, and phenotypic cancer-related data are being generated. However, access to this data is constrained by stringent governance frameworks designed to ensure compliance with complex local and international regulations, which, while essential for data protection, present significant barriers to cross-border discovery, access, and analysis. This deliverable aims to address these challenges by developing a seamless and interoperable access using open standards to data discovery, access and analysis platforms across different infrastructures, culminating in a demonstrator that highlights a complete user journey from data discovery to analysis.

The main institutions and services involved in the demonstrator are EMBL-EBI, CSC, UMCG/MOLGENIS, EGA, GDI and [Globus](#). The demonstrator leverages a synthetic dataset generated for EOSC4Cancer under Task 1.2, partitioned into sample-based datasets hosted at CSC in Finland, UMCG in the Netherlands and EMBL-EBI in the UK to simulate a federated data environment. Data governance responsibilities were also distributed with the access to the data hosted at EMBL-EBI managed via the EGA, while GDI oversaw permissions for the data hosted at CSC and UMCG. Data discovery would therefore be facilitated via the EOSC4Cancer catalogue, the EGA and the GDI user portals for these datasets respectively. Finally, the user would access the dataset via Globus for the EGA subset, and via remote compute nodes for the CSC/UMCG subsets. Federated datasets often fall under varying regulatory conditions, where certain resources may be freely accessed and downloaded upon approval, while others remain rigidly controlled, prohibiting any transfer outside designated secure environments. To illustrate both scenarios, this demonstrator incorporates two distinct access mechanisms. In the first scenario, data is retrieved through Globus, simulating a situation where, following authorisation, the dataset can be securely downloaded without jurisdictional restrictions. In contrast, the data hosted at CSC and UMCG represents a federated access scenario where the dataset remains within a secure remote computing environment, reflecting a model of data federation that restricts access by design, ensuring all analysis occurs locally without any external transfer of results. The demonstrator will therefore showcase the discovery of these datasets via the EOSC4Cancer, EGA and GDI portals respectively, request access after authenticating through a single user account on both sites, and access/analyse the datasets at the institutions also using the same authentication account. Authentication across all systems is unified through LifeSciences AAI (LS AAI), ensuring a seamless experience using a single identity. The demonstrator illustrates the full workflow, from dataset discovery and access requests to authenticated analysis, highlighting the viability of secure, interoperable, cross-institutional federated data access.

A simplified summary is shown below in [Figure 1](#).

Figure 1: Summary of workflow of demonstrator

Beside the main demonstrator, the BBMRI-ERIC ecosystem with its federated capabilities and cancer related resources was enhanced to facilitate discovery / analyses / access by piloting cBioPortal with additional image viewing capabilities and a Whole Slide Image (WSI) archive. Sustaining and further enhancing such mechanisms is a core activity at BBMRI-ERIC to empower researchers accessing the services.

3 Deliverable Report

The user journey encompasses the discovery and access of data across multiple cancer data services. To highlight the interoperable access to federated data across these services, the demonstrator is structured into multiple components, each corresponding to a specific service or institution. As part of Task 1.2, a synthetic dataset was generated by the BSC and subsequently ingested into the EGA for future distribution ([EGAD50000000276](#)). The dataset has been used to showcase the work done as part of the current deliverable, and for the broader objectives of interconnected work packages. This dataset was also prepared with inputs from WP4, which represent real-world use cases of cancer genomic data. An overview of the dataset, along with its accompanying metadata, is presented in [Figure 2](#).

The screenshot shows the EGA website interface for the dataset [EGAD50000000276](#). The page title is "EOSC4Cancer Longitudinal Synthetic Colorectal Cancer Genomic data developed at BSC". The description states: "The synthetic genomes have been created trying to mimic real cancer data of 4 patients (Named 185,186,187 and 188). Mutations are based on real CRC patients from the PCAWG dataset. For each patient, two tumor samples at different time points and one healthy sample have been simulated. The cancer intra-tumor heterogeneity and evolution in the patients is depicted by simulating reads from tumor subclones separately and then mixing them according to their clonal proportions in each sample. For rapid use and transfer only selected chromosomes have been generated for each patient."

Chromosomes per patient:

- 185: chr4, chr5, chr7, chr17
- 186: chr1, chr7, chr12, chr17
- 187: chr1, chr2, chr5, chr12, chr17
- 188: chr2, chr5, chr12, chr13, chr17

Workflows used to create BAM/BAI, VCF and MAF files from FASTQ (Alignment with GRCh38):

- <https://usegalaxy.eu/published/workflow?id=2c3d05029c02113e>
- <https://usegalaxy.eu/published/workflow?id=1da86d74f8535f4e>

09/02/2024 8 samples DAC: [EGAC00001000514](#) Technology: unspecified

Access Policy 1 Study History 64 Files (427.8 GB) Metadata Request Access

EGA public datasets
This policy is affiliated to the open access datasets archived at the EGA. Datasets are not subject to controlled access and, as a result, may be distributed without the requirement of a data access application.

Figure 2: Discovery of EOSC4Cancer dataset on the EGA website

This dataset was split into three parts for the purposes of this demonstrator, as described in [Section 2](#). The first phase of the demonstrator describes the process of discovering and accessing the dataset hosted at EMBL-EBI and managed by the EGA while the second phase addresses the process for accessing the data hosted at CSC managed by GDI. These components are described in detail below.

1. Discovery via EOSC4Cancer catalogue, GDI or EGA

In a previous report we have described the MOLGENIS based EOSC4Cancer catalogue (D1.1). With this deliverable, we aim to expand the user journey from discovery of all Cancer data towards requesting specific data modalities, in particular genomic data. We therefore implemented the following components:

First, we have loaded the synthetic data into the EOSC4Cancer catalogue simulating genomics data attached to, e.g., a large cancer cohort study having many types of data ([Figure 3](#)).

The screenshot displays the EOSC4Cancer catalogue interface. At the top, there are two tabs: 'DETAILED' and 'COMPACT'. Below the tabs, it indicates '2 collections'. The first collection is titled 'EGAD50000000276' and includes a description: 'The synthetic genomes have been created trying to mimic real cancer data of 4 patients (Named 185,186,187 and 188). Mutations are based on real CRC patients from the PCAWG dataset. For each patient, two tumor samples at different time points and one ...'. Below the description is a table with columns: Type, Design, Participants, and Duration. The 'Type' is 'Clinical trial' and 'Duration' is 'not available'. The second collection is titled 'EGAD50000000564' and includes a description: 'This dataset contains 10 tumor and normal pairs synthetic WGS data of colorectal cancer that were simulated in a standard format of Illumina paired-end reads. The NEAT read simulator (version 3.0, https://github.com/zstephens/neat-genreads) was utili ...'. Below the description is a table with columns: Type, Design, Participants, and Duration. The 'Type' is 'Clinical trial' and 'Duration' is 'not available'. At the bottom, there is a pagination control showing 'PAGE 1 OF 1'.

Type	Design	Participants	Duration
Clinical trial			not available

Type	Design	Participants	Duration
Clinical trial			not available

Figure 3: Synthetic data listed on EOSC4Cancer catalogue

Then we added DCAT semantic annotation to the EOSC4Cancer catalogue ([Figure 4](#)) such that its content can be harvested by other catalogues, specifically GDI portal.

```
<http://demo-rd3.molgenis.net/test-
eosoc/api/rdf/Resources/id=EGAS50000000190> a Test-eosc:Resources,
  qb:Observation, ldp:DirectContainer, dcat:Catalog;
  dcat:endpointURL <http://demo-rd3.molgenis.net/test-eosc/api/rdf>;
  fdp-o:metadataIdentifier <http://demo-rd3.molgenis.net/test-
eosoc/api/rdf/Resources/id=EGAS50000000190>;
  qb:dataSet Test-eosc:Resources;
  rdfs:label "EGAS50000000190";
  <http://demo-rd3.molgenis.net/test-eosc/api/rdf/Resources/column/rdfT:
dcat:Catalog;
  ldp:membershipResource <http://demo-rd3.molgenis.net/test-
eosoc/api/rdf/Endpoint/id=main_fdp>;
  <http://demo-rd3.molgenis.net/test-
eosoc/api/rdf/Resources/column/fdpEndpoint> <http://demo-
rd3.molgenis.net/test-eosc/api/rdf/Endpoint/id=main_fdp>;
  ldp:hasMemberRelation fdp-o:metadataCatalog;
  <http://demo-rd3.molgenis.net/test-
eosoc/api/rdf/Resources/column/ldpMembershipRelation>
  fdp-o:metadataCatalog;
  dcterms:identifier "EGAS50000000190";
  <http://demo-rd3.molgenis.net/test-eosc/api/rdf/Resources/column/id>
"EGAS50000000190";
  dcterms:title "EOSC4Cancer Synthetic Colorectal Cancer Genomic data";
```

Figure 4: Example DCAT export from the EOSC4Cancer catalog

Finally we implemented a data selection and request feature to EOSC4Cancer catalogue to facilitate data access requests to the individual level data source, e.g. GDI, shown in Figure 5. The implementation of this feature has been inspired by BBMRI-Directory implementation where the MOLGENIS based catalogue provides a similar user interaction to hand-over requests for biobank samples and data to the BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator component. We envision that in the future multiple relevant request frameworks might be connected within this approach, e.g. enabling GDI requests, BBMRI requests, EUCAIM requests, etc.

Figure 5: EOSC4Cancer request pilot. Note the shopping cart icon added to each dataset and the request from GDI button.

Finally, this selection then could be passed to the GDI by clicking the “Request from GDI” button. This is not yet fully functional awaiting work from the GDI team (who has gracefully supported us in this part of the pilot). Strategically, we envision the MOLGENIS catalogue team to implement this feature to link to all kinds of relevant data repositories, not only GDI so data request scenarios crossing different infrastructures can be supported in a user friendly way. We expect this work to be sustained in follow up projects, including granted UNCAN-connect.

2. User journey via EGA

a. The European Genome-phenome Archive

[Figure 2](#) shows the relevant information for the data hosted at the EGA including an option to request access by the user. Under the standard operational framework of the EGA, access to datasets requires users to register for an account. Once an access request is submitted, it undergoes evaluation by the corresponding Data Access Committee (DAC), which holds authority over the governance of data access for the associated study. The outcome of this decision—approval or denial—is automatically communicated to the requester via email.

As part of the deliverable, changes were made to the authentication and access mechanisms at the EGA by integrating support for the Life Science Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (LS AAI). This development facilitates federated identity access across

infrastructures, while maintaining compatibility with existing EGA account management systems. The login user interface is depicted in [Figure 6](#).

Figure 6: Authentication via LS AAI at the EGA distribution interface

A user-friendly interface was also developed to allow for persistent linkage between an EGA user account and an LS AAI federated identity, as shown in [Figure 7](#).

Link Accounts

EGA - LS AAI

Figure 7: Linkage of EGA and LS AAI accounts

Users opting to authenticate via LS AAI are redirected to the Life Science Research Infrastructure (LS RI) login service, which serves as the central broker for LS Login-based authentication. This redirection is shown below in [Figure 8](#).

EMBL-EBI

Login to Life Science Login

LIFE SCIENCE RI

Life Science Login is a common gateway to the European Life Sciences research Infrastructures

Username

as42

Password

.....

Don't Remember Login

Clear prior granting of permission for release of your information to this service.

Figure 8: Authentication of user accounts via LS AAI redirected from the EGA user interface

Upon successful authentication, users are forwarded to a new distribution user interface developed as part of this deliverable. This interface consolidates and presents all datasets and associated files for which the user has been granted access. This interface is illustrated in [Figure 9](#).

User: as42@ebi.ac.uk

EGA Dataset and File Viewer

This page allows you to view datasets and their associated files. You can select files to request for download. Once you select the desired files, click the 'Request Download' button.

[Request Download](#)

Dataset Stable Id	Dataset Description
EGAD50000000276	EOESC4Cancer Longitudinal Synthetic Colorectal Cancer Genomic data

File Id	File Name	File Size
EGAF50000086812	185tumor2_read1.fq.gz	12291864574
EGAF50000086813	185tumor2_read2.fq.gz	12291821283
EGAF50000086815	185tumor_read1.fq.gz	13480027244
EGAF50000086814	185tumor_read2.fq.gz	13480119277
EGAF50000086846	FAKEID099-2_data_mutations.txt	7644
EGAF50000086871	FAKEID099_data_mutations.txt	15522
EGAF50000086852	Galaxy1-[first_sequencing_-_norm...	2690932
EGAF50000086853	Galaxy1-[first_sequencing_-_norm...	21175734423
EGAF50000086858	Galaxy2-[first_sequencing_-_tumo...	2701900

Figure 9: EGA distribution interface

The interface presents a navigable list of datasets on the left-hand pane, and upon selecting a dataset, users are shown the corresponding files available for download.

The standard data access mechanism at the EGA is facilitated through a command-line-based Python client, which allows users to programmatically retrieve authorised files. To mitigate usability challenges associated with this approach—particularly for non-technical users—a new data delivery system has been developed that leverages the Globus platform as the principal mechanism for secure and scalable file transfer.

When a user submits a request and it gets approved by DAC, the relevant files can be retrieved from EGA's long-term archival storage, decrypted, re-encrypted using a user-specific encryption scheme, and bundled into a collection hosted on a designated Globus endpoint. Once the process is complete, a notification containing access details and decryption instructions is dispatched to the user's registered email address.

b. Globus

As elaborated in [Section 2](#), the Globus platform supports both its native authentication protocol and federated authentication via LS AAI. This interoperability enables users to log in to Globus using the same federated identity previously utilised within the EGA environment. The authentication process is depicted in [Figure 10](#).

Figure 10: Authentication via LS AAI on Globus

Upon successful login, users can browse and search for data collections that either belong to them or have been explicitly shared with them by others. [Figure 11](#) shows access to a collection called EGA Distribution Test that includes the previously requested files.

Figure 11: List of shared collections on Globus

The contents of these collections are consistent with the datasets and files previously selected within the EGA interface (see [Figure 6](#)), and are further visualised in [Figure 12](#).

Figure 12: List of requested files available for access via Globus

Once accessed, these files can be downloaded directly to the user’s local machine or synchronised with their personal Globus endpoints for downstream processing. Decryption can then be carried out using the instructions provided.

In summary, phase 1 demonstrates the successful integration of federated authentication and streamlined data distribution within the EGA ecosystem. By incorporating LS AAI for secure, unified access and leveraging Globus for efficient file transfer, the demonstrator enables users to seamlessly authenticate, request, and retrieve datasets across platforms. These enhancements significantly improve usability and interoperability, aligning with the broader objectives of enabling cross-institutional data access within a federated infrastructure.

3. User journey via GDI

This phase extends the demonstrator’s federated access capabilities by showcasing the ingestion, discovery, and controlled access of synthetic datasets within the Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) framework. This also highlights how the integration of LS AAI and coordinated governance models enables secure, cross-institutional data access via the GDI Portal and CSC infrastructure, further reinforcing the demonstrator’s emphasis on interoperability and compliance in a federated data environment.

a. Genomic Data Infrastructure

The second phase of the demonstrator involves access to the dataset hosted at CSC, with access managed through the GDI Portal. [Figure 13](#) illustrates the process of dataset discovery within the GDI Portal.

The screenshot displays the EGDI portal interface. At the top, the navigation menu includes 'Home', 'Datasets', 'Allele Frequency', 'Themes', 'Publishers', 'About', a shopping cart icon, and a 'Login' button. The 'European Genomic Data Infrastructure' logo is on the left. A search bar contains the text 'CSC Cancer' and shows '1 dataset found'. On the left side, there are three filter menus: 'Access Rights', 'Themes', and 'Keywords'. The main content area shows a dataset card for 'HEALTH Finnish EOSC4Cancer Synthetic Data Demonstrator'. The card description states: 'Dataset containing 2 samples from the Longitudinal Synthetic Colorectal Cancer Genomic data developed at BSC (EGAD50000000276)'. It also includes metadata: 'Created on 19 March 2025', 'Modified on 19 March 2025', and 'Published by CSC - IT Center for Science (Finland)'. Below the description are four tags: 'C18.9', 'C2955', 'Cancer', and 'Colorectal'. An 'Add to basket' button is located at the bottom right of the dataset card.

Figure 13: Discovery of EOSC4Cancer synthetic dataset on GDI portal

In alignment with the previous services, LS AAI has also been integrated into the GDI Portal as a federated identity provider, enabling users to authenticate using a consistent identity across EGA, Globus, and GDI systems ([Figure 14](#)).

Figure 14: Authentication via LS AAI on GDI portal

Once authenticated, users are able to submit formal data access requests for datasets of interest. These requests typically require accompanying documentation, including ethical approval letters, a comprehensive project proposal, and a data analysis plan ([Figure 15](#)).

Figure 15: Application submission for access request on GDI portal

Similar to the EGA model, data access requests within GDI are evaluated by a dedicated governance body. However, an important distinction lies in the organisational structure: while the EGA operates through study-specific DACs, the GDI employs a centralised data governance framework. Another notable divergence is in the current data hosting architecture—whereas EGA datasets are stored centrally at EMBL-EBI (UK) or CRG (Spain), the GDI framework supports decentralised hosting across its federated nodes. This distinction is expected to diminish over time with the emergence of the [Federated EGA](#) (FEGA), which will introduce comparable mechanisms for decentralised data discovery and access. In the context of this demonstrator, CSC serves as the data host responsible for managing access to the relevant federated dataset. Once user permissions are approved via the GDI portal, access provisioning to the data is initiated by CSC.

b. IT Center for Science (CSC)

To complete the end-to-end federated access journey, LS AAI has also been implemented as an alternative authentication mechanism within CSC's internal infrastructure ([Figure 16](#)). This provides a seamless and consistent user experience across all components of the demonstrator. CSC allows a user to link their CSC identity to their LS AAI identity, using the GA4GH LinkedIdentities visa. This means that a user who wishes to access data on CSC compute resources using their LS identity must a) have a CSC account, and b) link the CSC account to their LS identity.

Figure 16: Authentication via LS AAI at CSC

Multi-factor authentication is required to access CSC Sensitive Data Services, for example via an authenticator app on a mobile phone. This can also be set up as part of the LS AAI authentication service, as shown in [Figure 17](#).

Figure 17: Multi-factor authentication via LS AAI

Successful authentication to this service gives users access to their sensitive data services, including datasets authorised for the user via GDI. This capability is supported via the GA4GH ControlledAccessGrants visa, which is generated by the GDI central User Portal, and read by SDS at CSC to determine which GDI administered datasets the user has access to. SD Desktop is a virtualised desktop platform that allows users to create, or use pre-existing, virtual machines for accessing data within an SPE. Once logged into SD Desktop, the user can utilise a virtual machine to access the authorised datasets as shown in [Figure 18](#).

Figure 18: Access to virtual machines at CSC after successful authentication

Once a user spins up and logs into a virtual machine, (e.g. Ubuntu as shown in [Figure 19](#)), the user can use Data Gateway service, which acts as the access point for the GDI datasets, including the federated dataset to be accessed within the demonstrator, by reading the

ControlledAccessGrants visa generated by the GDI User Portal. It should be noted that other visa sources can also be used, so that SD Desktop can allow access to authorised datasets administered by other DACs.

Figure 19: Access to Data Gateway Service via virtual machines

The Data Gateway then reads the identifiers of all the datasets at CSC the user has access to and mounts them into a virtual folder for access via a FUSE layer, enabling read-access to the data, as shown in [Figure 20](#).

Figure 20: Read access to datasets provided via Data Gateway

Once the files have been successfully mounted via the FUSE layer, the user is then able to access the files either directly via a file browser ([Figure 21](#)) or run remote analyses on these files via a terminal ([Figure 22](#)).

Figure 21: Access to requested files via file browser

Figure 22: Access to requested files via terminal

As mentioned in [Section 2](#), the dataset at CSC is aimed at simulating a trusted research environment (TRE) with no access outside this remote instance. Therefore, any analyses would be restricted to this environment with no possibility of exporting files or results without confirmation from the administrator of the VM, thus fulfilling the requirements of interoperable federated data access.

A stretch goal for the demonstrator was to facilitate distributed or federated analysis, for example from a centralised orchestrator. GA4GH have defined the Task Execution Service (TES), which is a standardised way of executing tasks on a remote SPE or other compute resources. CSC deployed a TES endpoint, which allowed an authenticated user with an LS identity, to execute a TES described task on ePouta, the CSC hosted SPE. The task(s) could be executed on data hosted or transferred to the SPE, and the results generated. In this instance, the analysis results were uploaded to an s3 bucket which the user could access via the LS AAI. This system does not allow interactive analysis of the data, for example viewing raw data files, but does allow the results of an analysis to be returned to the user. Additionally the number and type of analyses performed on a particular dataset can be restricted, depending on the use case. Such a federated or distributed system could also be utilised to analyse data in a harmonised way, for example by running a variant calling and annotation pipeline, in multiple nodes, prior to uploading the results into a visualisation tool such as cBioPortal.

In conclusion, phase 2 illustrates the implementation of secure, federated data access through the GDI Portal and CSC infrastructure, highlighting how centralised governance, federated authentication via LS AAI, and secure remote analysis environments can be effectively combined to support responsible data sharing. Together with the developments described in phase 1, the demonstrator provides a comprehensive, interoperable solution for accessing sensitive genomic data across distributed nodes. By enabling seamless authentication, controlled access, and secure analyses, the demonstrator fulfills its objectives and establishes a robust foundation for future federated data access frameworks within the broader research ecosystem.

A video of these sections of the demonstrator has been recorded for the deliverable and added to the project [Google drive](#).

c. University Medical Center Groningen (UMCG)

Via the UMCG cluster another variant of data access has been demonstrated. This model has been successfully used in EU project Solve-RD (Johansson et al, 2024¹) and will now be used in ERDERA, UNCAN-connect and other EU projects. Therefore it is strategically desirable to also integrate into the GDI landscape.

Following data request approval from GDI the local data manager grants permission and links a local user account (currently that is not automatic, a long running collaboration with LS AAI team is currently being implemented to directly sign in to UMCG High performance computing cluster using LS AAI). Optionally, for maximum security also a more shield solution is available where users first need to sign in to a windows remote desktop environment. This latter solution disables network traffic (airlock). However, for this demo the more open direct SSH option was chosen.

The data for the demonstrator is loaded in a separate GDI user group (one per access) to control user access to specific data.

¹ Johansson LF, Laurie S, Spalding D, Gibson S, Ruvolo D, Thomas C, Piscia D, de Andrade F, Been G, Bijlsma M, Brunner H, Cimerman S, Dizjikan FY, Ellwanger K, Fernandez M, Freeberg M, van de Geijn GJ, Kanninga R, Maddi V, Mehtarizadeh M, Neerincx P, Ossowski S, Rath A, Roelofs-Prins D, Stok-Benjamins M, van der Velde KJ, Veal C, van der Vries G, Wadsley M, Warren G, Zurek B, Keane T, Graessner H, Beltran S, Swertz MA, Brookes AJ; Solve-RD consortium. An interconnected data infrastructure to support large-scale rare disease research. *Gigascience*. 2024 Jan 2;13:giae058. doi: 10.1093/gigascience/giae058. PMID: 39302238; PMCID: PMC11413801.

```

/groups/umcg-gdi/tmp01/projects/ /eos4cancer-demo/datasets/EGAD5000000276/bam
[ @gearshift bam]$ ls
Galaxy7-[188_v2_normal].bai Galaxy8-[188-1_v2_tumor].bai Galaxy9-[188-2_v2_tumor].bai
Galaxy7-188_v2_normal.bai Galaxy8-188-1_v2_tumor.bai Galaxy9-188-2_v2_tumor.bai
Galaxy7-[188_v2_normal].bam Galaxy8-[188-1_v2_tumor].bam Galaxy9-[188-2_v2_tumor].bam
Galaxy7-188_v2_normal.bam Galaxy8-188-1_v2_tumor.bam Galaxy9-188-2_v2_tumor.bam

```

Figure 23: List of files available for access on the UMCG cluster

To make the demonstrator more realistic, we have implemented a routine analysis of the DNA variants in the synthetic data using the MOLGENIS VIP variant interpretation pipeline (<https://github.com/molgenis/vip>).

```

samplesheet188.tsv ×
Users > Desktop > eos4cancer > samplesheet188.tsv
1 individual_id cram
2 galaxy_7_188_normal datasets/EGAD5000000276/bam/Galaxy7-188_v2_normal.bam
3 galaxy_8_188_tumor datasets/EGAD5000000276/bam/Galaxy8-188-1_v2_tumor.bam
4 galaxy_9_188_tumor datasets/EGAD5000000276/bam/Galaxy9-188-2_v2_tumor.bam
5 |

eos4cancer.config ×
Users > Desktop > eos4cancer > eos4cancer.config
1 params {
2 // output assembly
3 assembly = "GRCh38"
4 // created using HpoMapperApp.java in https://github.com/molgenis/vip-utils
5 hpo_phenotypic_abnormality="${VIP_DIR_DATA}/resources/hpo_20240813_phenotypic_abnormality.tsv"
6
7 GRCh37 {
8 reference {
9 fasta = "${VIP_DIR_DATA}/resources/GRCh37/human_g1k_v37.fasta.gz"
10 fastaFai = "${VIP_DIR_DATA}/resources/GRCh37/human_g1k_v37.fasta.gz.fai"
11 fastaGzi = "${VIP_DIR_DATA}/resources/GRCh37/human_g1k_v37.fasta.gz.gzi"
12 }
13 chain {
14 GRCh38 = "${VIP_DIR}/resources/b37ToHg38.over.chain"
15 }
16 }
17
18 GRCh38 {
19 reference {
20 fasta = "/groups/umcg-gdi/tmp01/projects/umcg-jveen/eos4cancer-demo/resources/hg38.fa.gz"
21 fastaFai = "/groups/umcg-gdi/tmp01/projects/umcg-jveen/eos4cancer-demo/resources/hg38.fa.gz.fai"
22 fastaGzi = "/groups/umcg-gdi/tmp01/projects/umcg-jveen/eos4cancer-demo/resources/hg38.fa.gz.gzi"
23 }
24 }
25
26 T2T {
27 reference {
28 fasta = ""
29 fastaFai = ""
30 fastaGzi = ""
31 }
32 chain {
33 GRCh38 = "${VIP_DIR}/resources/chm13v2-hg38.over.chain.gz"
34 }
35 }
36 }
37

```

Figure 24: configuration of a MOLGENIS VIP custom workflow for the EOSC4Cancer data

This results in a user friendly report that can be shown to the user. This is a pipeline using nextflow, see [Figure 25](#) for an exemplary output.

Reported variants for galaxy_7_188_normal (sex:? at status:?)

3 records Sort by CAPICE (c

Position	Reference	Type	Proband	Effect	Gene	Inh.Pat.	H C
chr17:1230077	T	STR	<CNV:TR>/<CNV:TR>	upstream_gene_variant upstream_gene_variant	ABR ABR		
chr2:2332266	C	STR	<CNV:TR>/<CNV:TR>	upstream_gene_variant upstream_gene_variant upstream_gene_variant upstream_gene_variant upstream_gene_variant	MYT1L MYT1L MYT1L MYT1L MYT1L	AD AD AD AD AD	
chr2:50651472	A	STR	A/<CNV:TR>	feature_elongation, ... feature_elongation, ... feature_elongation, ... feature_elongation, ... feature_elongation, ... feature_elongation, ... feature_elongation, ... feature_elongation, ...	NRXN1 NRXN1 NRXN1 NRXN1 NRXN1 NRXN1 NRXN1 NRXN1	AD, AR AD, AR AD, AR AD, AR AD, AR AD, AR AD, AR AD, AR	

Figure 25: Example output from the EOSC4Cancer synthetic data

4. BBMRI-ERIC discovery / access workflow pilot

The BBMRI-ERIC IT-ecosystem is comprised of a fully operational discovery/access chain, with core components like BBMRI-ERIC Directory (based on MOLGENIS software and being a broad catalogue of biobanks with aggregated information on their collections that can be browsed and filtered by country, sample type, quality marks, ICD-10 and several more facets) and BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator (for facilitating access to samples and connected data) operated already for several years. For authentication and authorisation in the various services offered the BBMRI-ERIC AAI was used for several years which was then replaced by LifeScience AAI (LS AAI) partially developed by members of Common Service IT (CS IT) of BBMRI-ERIC.

The BBMRI-ERIC Directory was prepared to support Data Use Ontology (DUO) which will (with its human and machine-readable terms for use of assets) ease the processing of requests for data attached to samples and, thus, increase FAIRness of datasets. This will become even more important when making use of linkages between datasets. The creation of relevant DUO compliant descriptions for datasets listed in the EOSC4Cancer catalogue and the BBMRI-ERIC Directory will be next endeavours in establishing these services and their use by data holders to provide information to the users.

With the evolving needs in the BBMRI-ERIC community and the research communities the discovery mechanisms were extended by the so-called BBMRI-ERIC Federated Platform (FP), which adds greater flexibility and actuality to the descriptions offered by the biobanks in the

BBMRI community. The FP – a vendor neutral platform for discovery and analyses – currently consists of two components: the BBMRI-ERIC Finder for discovery and data analysis focused on clinical, phenotypic and genomics data and with a data model based on OMOP in a secure processing environment; and the BBMRI-ERIC Locator tool offering real-time searches for samples and associated data on record level. Finder is a tool from a commercial vendor (BC|Platforms) and the BBMRI-ERIC Locator is an open-source development by Deutsches Krebsforschungszentrum. Both platforms operate in a federated way with central services (Finder and Lens/Locator) and local connectors (BC|Link and Bridgehead) to data stores at the connected sites which can be dynamically updated from the source systems and appropriate ETL processes in place. Finder and Locator are operating based on OMOP and HL7/FHIR respectively for real-time discovery of samples and data.

The Colorectal Cancer (CRC) Cohort as a central cohort at BBMRI-ERIC (which was created with data from 26 European biobanks in the ADOPT project) was integrated into the Finder beside some other collections allowing to being discovered in running flexible searches on all data that are available for these collections. If considered interesting to a researcher data access and further analyses on the CRC-Cohort can be negotiated within the BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator and an expedite procedure is in place including an Access Committee (located at BBMRI-ERIC HQ acting as a controller) and a veto procedure regarding the various biobanks which have contributed to the CRC-Cohort.

For enlarging the capabilities for researchers utilising BBMRI-ERIC infrastructure further components regarding image data and their metadata were developed respectively integrated. The cBioPortal platform for Cancer Genomics is an open-access, open-source resource for interactive exploration of multidimensional cancer genomics data sets. The capabilities of cBioPortal (providing rapid, intuitive, and high-quality access to molecular profiles and clinical attributes from large-scale cancer genomics projects) allow researchers to translate rich data sets into biologic insights and clinical applications. This is supported by the possibility to integrate viewer modules like XNAT for radiology images or XOPat for viewing Whole Slide Images (WSI) as used in Digital Pathology.

cBioPortal and its usefulness for the BBMRI-ERIC IT infrastructure was piloted with the aim to add this as another component of the FP. Part of setup of this pilot were several steps:

- enhancing cBioPortal's AAI capabilities (make OAuth2 usable and configurable for third party providers)
- setting up cBioPortal instances
- integrating XOPat viewer into cBioPortal
- importing data into cBioPortal
- linking image archives with data in cBioPortal

The technical information on setting up the XOPat tool and connecting it to a cBioPortal instance was provided to guideline documents made available in EOESC4Cancer WP3.

As can be seen from above descriptions more and more components are feeding into the BBMRI-ERIC ecosystem that evolves over time. Each component on its own adds to use cases of research in the biobanks and biomolecular resources domain. Overall, the different capabilities add to complexity of the federation for the researchers (i.e. users of the IT systems) which makes necessary to wrap them in some way and create a unified discovery interface e.g. similar to the EJP-RD Virtual Platform (EJP-VP). The EJP-VP provides access to a growing network of FAIR resources for the rare disease research community. A unified discovery interface is foreseen for the next iteration of the BBMRI-ERIC CS IT.

a. Enhancing cBioPortal's AAI capabilities

cBioPortal is foreseen for open access on data but also provides functionality for controlling access on the data. cBioPortal allows configuring SAML or OIDC AAI integration. However, OIDC integration only works for selected Identity Providers (IdP), e.g. Keycloak, and enforces local user storage. For the whole BBMRI-ERIC IT-infrastructure single-sign-on with the LifeScience Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (LS AAI) is in use. This allows configuring detailed access for a variety of services for each user. Therefore, the cBioPortal functionality for access control was updated to include an appropriate interface to LS AAI. This mechanism allows logging in with credentials from a researcher of institutions that are registered in EDUGain. In addition, there is the possibility to request a LS Hostel account for logging in, which will be granted after appropriate checks by the AAI team.

Figure 26 shows Two-Factors-Authentication (2FA) – second step enforced to access cBioPortal hosting sensitive data. From the selection, only parts of the CRC-Cohorts dataset are visible, separated by institutions that provided the data.

Figure 26: Two-Factors-Authentication (2FA) to access cBioPortal hosting sensitive data.

b. Setting up cBioPortal instances

Two instances of cBioPortal were set up. One instance will be used for demonstration purposes and contains anonymised images and descriptive data. The other instance was established to host the data of BBMRI-ERIC's CRC-Cohort for deeper exploration by researchers. The data of more than 10.500 cases of colorectal cancer were contributed to this central BBMRI-ERIC collection by 26 biobanks from 12 European countries and are controlled by BBMRI-ERIC with an Access Committee in place at the HQ and an expedite procedure which shall allow access within one month after a request on the cohort was filed.

c. XOPat viewer and integration into cBioPortal

XOPat is a flexible whole-slide image viewer designed for integration within external systems. The requirement on the image archive is availability via a web URL. As XOPat is a web-based application, it provides several ways to view slides using URLs.

Next to the cBioPortal access control the WSI-viewing services are primarily using OAuth2 (support for SAML is extendable, but not implemented yet), so going for a uniform authentication login using one client (with one place that holds authentication and authorization information) was the intended way to go. It is necessary to understand that in its minimal version, the WSI viewing through the browser is dependent at least on one server (dedicated WSI servers or file servers) that delivers the whole slide image chunks. The WSI-Service was selected to deliver the slide data.

As the underlying WSI server was using OAuth2/OIDC, an OIDC module was introduced to the XOPat. The new module follows XOPat versatility design, allowing to configure for example the authentication flow and implementation (e.g. using redirection VS pop-up window) and to store the target login session to for example viewer's cookies or cache.

The WSI-Service was extended to handle LS AAI integration through OIDC, resolving access rights to individual slides.

These updates enable to

- have custom authorization logics, integrate with arbitrary authorities mapping
- customise OIDC integration within cBioPortal
a bug was discovered in cBioPortal, which uses different user models for SAML (mostly used by cBioPortal implementers) and OAuth2 (which was maybe not being used in production so far and thus the issue was hidden). The issue was documented in a Request for Comments (RFC), hopefully leading to a solution soon.
 - After successful authentication, the user must have corresponding local database entries or the login fails.
 - Lack of flexibility in parsing authorization data from third-party IDP
- configure cBioPortal and WSI-Service to require 2FA

The above-mentioned features were proposed as an implementation pull request to cBioPortal official repository, and a corresponding Request for Comments (RFC) was written.

Unfortunately, cBioPortal does not support other than study-level authorization access, so the CRC-Cohort could only be split by individual institutions, but no vertical data slicing was possible.

d. Importing data into cBioPortal and linking image archives with data in cBioPortal

Creating cBioPortal studies is done by importing CSV files describing a certain study. These files have a rigid structure – required headers, required field types in comments, required file structures (data and metadata files), references etc. But also programming converters for each system out there is impossible (tons of database structures, programming languages, custom API endpoints, excel sheets...). Since most storage systems support exporting to CSV files, a tool for converting and importing CSV files into cBioPortal was created which takes arbitrary CSV files and converts them to cBioPortal CSV format. Furthermore, it automates study management (import, update, delete operations) with the cBioPortal app (deployed via docker compose). csv2cbio automates study generation in cBioPortal-compatible-CSV format by a simple YAML description of individual study parts. It supports value filtering, file joins, custom functions, built-in utilities (UID generation) and more. The use of this tool allows creating multiple versions of studies in a fairly easy way.

e. Whole Slide Image archive

Whole slide images (WSIs) as digital representations of entire microscope slides, are an important tool in digital pathology. They will become more and more available in the future (e.g. Graz biobank currently has about 26 TB of WSI available). A number of such images used for a scientific paper on risks with image sharing² were anonymised and made available with corresponding descriptive data. Those WSIs can be discovered through a cBioPortal instance set up in the BBMRI-ERIC environment, where images and data can be browsed and by inspecting the images themselves. Both data and images can be used e.g. for training AI models. Training of models is usually dependent on the quality but also on the size of the available data set. Sustaining the cBioPortal with its content beyond the project duration and even enlarging the content in the future will increase the value of this offer and can best be achieved by research infrastructures like BBMRI-ERIC.

EMPAIA's wsi-server, one microservice of the standard's referential implementation was extended for the WSI-service to be usable as a standalone server with ability to:

² Holub, P., Müller, H., Bíl, T. et al. Privacy risks of whole-slide image sharing in digital pathology. Nat Commun 14, 2577 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-37991-y>

- support OAuth2 (or custom if added) authentication and authorization
- support for customizing data mapping logics: PathMapper, CSVMapper were implemented -> one can have custom ID system and logics that map them to the real data
- support for batch access (optimization) and API improvements (e.g. moving slide IDs to query parameters to allow filesystem paths to also act as IDs).

4 Discussion/next

steps

The work done for the deliverable effectively demonstrates a practical and scalable approach to federated data access across multiple, distinct infrastructures, underscoring both its technical feasibility and user-centric design considerations. By leveraging LS AAI for federated authentication, the system enables users to seamlessly navigate across the EOSC4Cancer, EGA, GDI and CSC systems using a single researcher identity. This streamlined authentication process not only simplifies access for users but also ensures compliance with stringent security and access control policies. The integration of Globus as a data distribution mechanism further augments the usability and reliability of data transfers, providing researchers with a robust and efficient alternative to more technically complex, programmatic methods.

A notable strength of this demonstrator lies in its modularity and reusability. The 'loosely coupled' protocol implemented in MOLGENIS to hand-over content between data request portals demonstrates the added value of link-based integration on top of a semantic (DCAT) interoperability layer. The interfaces and workflows developed are highly adaptable, with the potential for easy extension to additional nodes and repositories with minimal overhead. The successful implementation of secure remote environments at CSC, which incorporate access controls, dataset staging, and in situ analysis capabilities, illustrates how high-compliance use cases can be effectively addressed without compromising user autonomy or flexibility. UMCG demonstrates that similar experiences can be implemented across countries.

Looking ahead, a key area for further development is the incorporation of federated analysis capabilities that support distributed yet secure computation. While the current demonstrator enables seamless data access across federated nodes, subsequent iterations could introduce integrated analytical environments that allow users to run personalised, reproducible workflows directly within secure infrastructures. Platforms such as Galaxy provide an ideal model for this, offering web-based interfaces for users to execute complex bioinformatics pipelines without requiring direct access to raw data, possibly extended with privacy preserving protocols such as DataSHIELD or Vantage6. Embedding such workflow environments within the federated framework would enable researchers to perform targeted analyses—such as variant calling, expression quantification, or cohort comparisons—without transferring sensitive data outside of secure domains. This approach would further optimise computational efficiency, safeguard data privacy, and align with the broader goals of data sovereignty and FAIR principles.

Moreover, the potential integration of the demonstrator with cancer research portals, such as cBioPortal, could yield substantial benefits. cBioPortal offers interactive visualisation and analysis tools for cancer genomics data, and its integration with federated access systems would enable researchers to directly access, analyse, and visualise distributed datasets within a unified interface. This would create a streamlined pipeline from data discovery to in-depth analysis and visualisation, further simplifying and accelerating the research process. Such integration would require careful attention to ensuring interoperability across data formats, authentication protocols, and analytical tools between systems.

Finally, the ongoing development of Federated EGA (FEGA) presents an opportunity to align even more closely with the GDI model, thereby facilitating a more consistent user experience

and data access pathways regardless of the hosting infrastructure. Achieving alignment in metadata standards, data discovery protocols, and access request processes across these federated systems will be critical to enhancing interoperability and ensuring their continued evolution in line with the growing demands of large-scale genomic research. In addition, lightweight protocols such as originally created between BBMRI-ERIC Directory and Locator which now inspired the handover between EOSC4Cancer catalogue and GDI, will enable seamless user journeys across these infrastructures. Strategically, we envision the MOLGENIS catalogue team to implement this feature to link to all kinds of relevant data repositories, not only GDI but for example also EUCAIM so data request scenarios crossing different infrastructures can be supported in a user-friendly way .

BBMRI-ERIC foresees making the two cBioPortal instances with WSI archives and viewer operational and integrate these into the discovery / access infrastructure at BBMRI-ERIC. For better user experience for the researchers using the infrastructure a unified access point to the various components (catalogue and federated platform) is planned.

On technical level work on the XOpac viewer component will continue on extending the underlying popular high-resolution viewing library OpenSeadragon (<https://openseadragon.github.io> which XOpac builds on) with new rendering capabilities and data handling logics. This includes introducing data types, async cache and a type conversion pipeline. This will allow work on a native WebGL renderer that will be performant enough to deliver complex visualizations at interactive frames and thus provide improved usability to the researcher using this component. A proof-of-concept implementation already exists. This implementation needs being tested and integrated within XOpac, from which it took the inspiration in designing the interface. The renderer removes some limitations to the XOpac viewer (related to input data structure) and enables implementation of additional features.

In conclusion, the deliverable represents a significant advancement in the establishment of interoperable, federated data access across European research infrastructures. It provides a strong foundation upon which future developments, including federated analyses and integration with platforms like cBioPortal, can be built, thus contributing to the continued evolution of data access and collaborative research within the field of cancer genomics. We expect this work to be sustained in follow up projects, including granted UNCAN-connect.

5 List of abbreviations used

Abbreviation	Link
CRC	Colorectal Cancer
CSC	IT Center for Science (Finland)
DAC	Data Access Committee
EGA	European Genome-phenome Archive
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EUCAIM	<i>EUropean Federation for CAncer IMages</i>
EMBL-EBI	European Molecular Biology Laboratory - European Bioinformatics Institute
EOESC4CANCER	European Open Science Cloud for Cancer
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load process
FEGA	Federated European Genome-phenome Archive
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GDI	Genomic Data Infrastructure

Abbreviation	Link
HL7 / FHIR	Health Level 7 / Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
LS AAI	Life Sciences Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
LS RI	Life Science Research Infrastructure
MOLGENIS	MOLGENIS open source data platform
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
SD Desktop	Sensitive Data Desktop
SDS	Sensitive Data Services
SPE	Secure Processing Environment
TES	Task Execution Service
UMCG	University Medical Center Groningen

6 List of external links

Entity	Link
ADOPT project	https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/scientific-collaboration/adopt-bbmri-eric/
BBMRI-ERIC CRC-Cohort	https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/scientific-collaboration/colorectal-cancer-cohort
BBMRI-ERIC Directory	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/
BBMRI-ERIC	https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/
BBMRI-ERIC Finder	https://finder.bbmri-eric.eu/
BBMRI-ERIC Locator	https://locator.bbmri-eric.eu/
BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator	https://www.bbmri.it/en/negotiator/
BC Platforms	https://www.bcplatforms.com/
BSC	https://www.bsc.es/
cBioPortal	https://www.cbioportal.org/
CSV converter to cBioPortal	https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/csv2cbio
cBioPortal instances at BBMRI-ERIC	https://cbioportal.wsi-archive.bbmri-eric.eu https://cbioportal.crc-cohort.bbmri-eric.eu
CSC	https://csc.fi/en/
CSC remote services	https://sd-desktop.csc.fi/guacamole/#/
DataSHIELD	https://datashield.org/

Entity	Link
Data Use Ontology (DUO)	https://www.ga4gh.org/product/data-use-ontology-duo/
EDUGain	https://edugain.org
EGA	https://ega-archive.org/
EJP-RD VP (European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases Virtual Platform)	https://vp.ejprarediseases.org
EMBL-EBI	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/
EMPAIA	https://www.empaia.org
EOSC4CANCER	https://eosc4cancer.eu/
EOSC4Cancer catalogue	https://data-catalogue.molgeniscloud.org/
FEGA	https://ega-archive.org/about/projects-and-funders/federated-ega/
GA4GH	https://www.ga4gh.org/
Galaxy	https://usegalaxy.org/
GDI	https://login.gdi.com/Login/Login
GDI Portal	https://portal.dev.gdi.lu/
Globus	https://www.globus.org/
LS AAI	https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/
MOLGENIS	http://github.com/molgenis/molgenis-emx2

Entity	Link
MOLGENIS Catalogue	https://molgenis.org/
UMCG	https://www.umcg.nl/
Vantage	https://distributedlearning.ai/
WSI-Service	https://github.com/RationAI/WSI-Service/
XNAT	https://www.xnat.org
XOpat	https://github.com/RationAI/xopat https://xopat.readthedocs.io/en/latest/docs/web/xopat_configuration/#dynamic-configuration-opening-the-viewer